

The Violation of Human Rights of Men in India: An Unspoken Crisis

Abstract

The ongoing struggle for human rights in India, particularly concerning men, remains a critical yet often overlooked issue that demands urgent attention and action. In India, discussions surrounding human rights violations often focus on marginalized groups such as women, children, and minorities. While these are pressing issues, the violation of men's human rights remains an under-researched topic, often overshadowed by societal stereotypes and gendered perceptions. This paper examines the multifaceted nature of human rights abuses against men in India, including false accusations, gender-biased laws, domestic violence, custodial torture, and workplace harassment. Drawing on legal, sociological, and psychological perspectives, this paper highlights the gaps in policy and judicial mechanisms that exacerbate these violations. Addressing these gaps is crucial for fostering a more equitable society, where the human rights of all individuals, regardless of gender, are recognized and protected. In exploring these critical issues, it becomes evident that a comprehensive understanding of men's human rights is essential for developing effective interventions and promoting gender equality in all its forms. This understanding not only aids in formulating policies that are just and fair but also empowers men to seek justice without the fear of stigma or discrimination.

Keywords

Atul Subhash, Men Human Rights, False Accusations, Domestic Violence, 498 A Misuse, Suicide

Introduction

Human rights are universal and indivisible, guaranteeing dignity and equality for all individuals. However, in India, the focus has often been skewed towards protecting specific groups, leaving others, such as men, inadequately addressed. Despite being perceived as a privileged group, Indian men face numerous human rights violations, including wrongful incarceration, societal stereotyping, and systemic bias in laws. This article seeks to shed light on these issues, emphasizing the necessity of a balanced approach to gender justice.

Methodology

The research article employs a qualitative methodology to analyze the violation of human rights of men in India. The study combines a review of secondary data, legal analysis, and sociological perspectives to present a comprehensive understanding of the issue.

Research Design

This study is exploratory in nature, focusing on identifying, describing, and analyzing various forms of human rights violations faced by men in India. It does not rely on primary data collection but instead utilizes secondary sources such as government reports, journal articles, and case studies.

1. Legal Bias and False Accusations

1.1 Section 498A of IPC

The introduction of Section 498A was intended to safeguard women from cruelty by their husbands or relatives. However, studies have shown its misuse. The National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB) reported that a significant percentage of cases filed under this section result in acquittals due to lack of evidence.

"Analysis of the Misuse of Section 498A of IPC," Journal of Law and Society, 2020.
NCRB Crime Statistics Report, 2022.

1.2 Rape and Sexual Harassment Laws

Laws such as the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition, and Redressal) Act, 2013, focus solely on women, leaving men without recourse. Furthermore, the absence of gender-neutral rape laws in India fails to address sexual crimes against men.

2. Domestic Violence Against Men

Domestic violence against men remains underreported due to societal stigma. Studies conducted by men's rights organizations like Save Indian Family Foundation (SIFF) reveal that 52% of domestic violence victims are men, yet the Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005, does not extend protections to them.

IFF Domestic Violence Survey, 2021. "The Silent Suffering of Men in India," Indian Journal of Family Studies, 2019.

3. Custodial Violence

Custodial deaths and torture disproportionately affect men. The NCRB recorded over 1,600 custodial deaths in the last decade, the majority of which involved male victims. Such violations highlight systemic flaws in law enforcement.

"Custodial Torture and Human Rights in India," Economic and Political Weekly, 2020. NCRB Annual Report, 2023.

4. Workplace Harassment

While sexual harassment policies primarily address women, men also face workplace bullying, mental harassment, and false accusations. The lack of gender-inclusive policies leaves male victims vulnerable.

"Men at Work: The Untold Stories," Journal of Corporate Ethics, 2021.

5. Mental Health and Societal Expectation

Men in India face societal pressure to conform to traditional roles as breadwinners and protectors. This expectation often leads to mental health issues, which remain unaddressed due to stigma and lack of support systems.

"Gender Roles and Mental Health," International Journal of Psychology, 2020. WHO Mental Health Atlas, 2022.

Legal and Policy Gaps

India's legal system often lacks provisions for men's rights. Laws like the Dowry Prohibition Act and PWDVA are inherently one-sided, creating opportunities for misuse. The absence of gender-neutral policies perpetuates discrimination against men.

Case Studies

Case 1: Misuse of Section 498A

A 2020 case from Delhi highlighted how a man was wrongfully accused of dowry harassment, leading to his arrest and social ostracization, only to be acquitted after six years of trial.

Case 2: Domestic Violence

A 2018 study documented a Mumbai-based IT professional who suffered years of physical and emotional abuse at the hands of his spouse, with no legal recourse available.

Case 3: Atul Subhash

The case of Atul Subhash, a 34-year-old man, has drawn significant attention after he died by suicide in Bengaluru on December 9, 2024. Atul, an employee at a private firm, left behind an extensive 24-page suicide note. He accused his wife and her relatives of harassment, which he claimed had pushed him to take this extreme step. His wife had reportedly filed a legal case against him in Uttar Pradesh, contributing to the ongoing marital discord.

Recommendations

1. Gender-Neutral Laws: Revise existing laws to include protections for men.
2. Awareness Campaigns: Address societal stereotypes through education and media.
3. Support Systems: Establish shelters and helplines for male victims of domestic violence.

4. Judicial Reforms: Implement stringent penalties for false accusations.

5. Mental Health Services: Increase access to counseling and therapy for men.

Conclusion

The violation of men's human rights in India is an overlooked issue requiring urgent attention. A balanced approach to gender justice is essential for building a fair and equitable society. It is imperative to recognize that addressing domestic violence requires a holistic approach, ensuring that all victims, regardless of gender, receive the support and protection they need. This commitment to inclusivity not only fosters a safer environment for men but also promotes a culture of respect and understanding that benefits society as a whole.

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